

A Study on Investors Perception Towards Selected Mutual Fund Schemes Concerning to Thane Region

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Abstract:

Mutual funds have emerged as one of the most significant investment avenues in India due to their ability to offer diversification, professional fund management and flexible investment options to investors. With increasing financial literacy, urbanization and rising disposable income, investors are gradually shifting from traditional investment instruments towards market-linked products such as mutual funds. However, the perception of investors towards mutual fund schemes varies depending on their awareness level, demographic profile, risk tolerance, expected returns and satisfaction with fund performance.

The present study aims to analyze the perception of investors towards selected mutual fund schemes concerning the Thane region. The study focuses on four major aspects: awareness of mutual funds, investment pattern and scheme preference, risk–return perception and satisfaction level of investors. The research also examines the influence of demographic factors such as age, gender, income, education and occupation on investors' perception and decision-making process.

The study is based on both primary and secondary data. Primary data has been collected through a structured questionnaire circulated among investors in the Thane region using Google Forms, while secondary data has been sourced from journals, research papers, etc. The findings of the study are expected to provide valuable insights to mutual fund companies, financial advisors and policymakers in designing effective investor awareness programs and improving investor satisfaction towards mutual fund investments.

Keywords: Mutual Funds, Investors' Perception, Awareness, Risk–Return, Satisfaction.

Introduction:

Investment decisions play a crucial role in achieving financial stability and long-term wealth creation. In the present dynamic financial environment, investors are constantly searching for investment options that provide higher returns with manageable risk. Among the various investment alternatives available, mutual funds have gained prominence due to their ability to pool funds from investors and invest in

diversified portfolios of securities such as equity, debt and money market instruments.

A mutual fund is a professionally managed investment vehicle that allows investors to participate in capital markets without requiring extensive financial knowledge. Mutual fund schemes offer various options such as equity funds, debt funds, hybrid funds, index funds etc. catering to different risk appetites and investment horizons.

Despite the rapid growth of mutual funds, investors' perception towards these instruments is influenced by several factors including awareness, risk perception, expected returns, market volatility and past investment experiences. Many investors still hesitate to invest due to fear of risk, lack of knowledge and misconceptions regarding market-linked investments. Hence, understanding investors' perception becomes essential to analyze their investment behavior and preferences.

Thane region, being one of the rapidly developing urban areas near Mumbai, comprises investors from diverse demographic backgrounds such as salaried employees, professionals, students, businesspersons and homemakers. Their perception towards mutual fund investments varies based on income levels, education, occupation and financial goals. Therefore, this study attempts to analyze investors' perception towards selected mutual fund schemes concerning the Thane region with special reference to awareness, investment pattern, risk–return perception and satisfaction level.

Research Methodology:

Research Design:

The present study is descriptive in nature and aims to analyze the perception of investors towards selected mutual fund schemes in the Thane region. The study focuses on awareness, investment pattern, risk–return perception and satisfaction level of investors.

Objectives of the Study:

- To study the level of awareness of investors towards mutual funds as an investment option in the Thane region.
- To analyze the investment pattern and preference of investors towards selected mutual fund schemes.
- To examine the risk–return perception of investors regarding mutual fund

investments.

- To study the satisfaction level and overall perception of investors towards the performance of selected mutual fund schemes.

Sample Size: - In this study, 206 investors were considered from the Thane Region.

Data Collection: - The study is based on both primary and secondary data.

Hypothesis: -

- Hypothesis 1:

H0: There is no significant relationship between demographic factors and awareness of mutual fund investments.

H1: There is a significant relationship between demographic factors and awareness of mutual fund investments.

- Hypothesis 2:

H0: There is no significant relationship between demographic factors and preference towards selected mutual fund schemes.

H1: There is a significant relationship between demographic factors and preference towards selected mutual fund schemes.

- Hypothesis 3:

H0: There is no significant relationship between investors' risk tolerance and their perception of risk and return in mutual fund investments.

H1: There is a significant relationship between investors' risk tolerance and their perception of risk and return in mutual fund investments.

- Hypothesis 4:

H0: There is no significant relationship between investors' satisfaction level and the performance of selected mutual fund schemes.

H1: There is a significant relationship between investors' satisfaction level and

the performance of selected mutual fund schemes.

Review of Literature:

Md. Ilyas and Dr. N. Ramanjaneyulu (2025) Investors' Perception and Attitude towards Mutual Fund Investments through Upstox

The study examines investor perception and attitude towards mutual fund investments made through the digital platform Upstox. Primary data was collected from 100 respondents using a structured questionnaire. The findings reveal that most investors prefer a moderate-risk and moderate-return strategy. Fund performance and availability of diversified investment options were the most influential factors in fund selection. Although investors appreciated the ease of access and low cost of digital platforms, concerns were raised regarding customer service quality, lack of transparency, and inadequate investor education. The study concludes that

improving digital support systems and financial awareness can enhance investor confidence and satisfaction in online mutual fund platforms.

Dr. M. S. Kamalaveni et al. (2024) – A Study on Investor Perception towards Selecting Mutual Fund Schemes with Special Reference to Salem

This research focuses on understanding investor perception while selecting mutual fund schemes in Salem district. The study used a sample size of 150 respondents and applied statistical tools such as descriptive statistics, ANOVA, and reliability tests. The results indicate that demographic factors such as age, education, income, and occupation significantly influence mutual fund selection. Investors showed higher preference towards equity and index funds, while risk tolerance and financial aspirations like retirement planning and wealth creation played a crucial role in decision-making. The study highlights that past performance, liquidity, and diversification are the key determinants of investor satisfaction.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Demographic Factors:

Variables	Category	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	102	49.5
	Female	104	50.5
	Total	206	100
Age Group	Below 25 years	134	65.0
	25–35 years	46	22.3
	36–45 years	15	7.3
	46–55 years	6	2.9
	Above 55 years	5	2.5
	Total	206	100
Occupation	Student	91	44.2
	Salaried Employee	72	35.0
	Business	23	11.2
	Self-Employed	14	6.8
	Professional	5	2.4
	Retired	1	0.4
	Total	206	100
Monthly Income (₹)	Below 25,000	112	54.4
	25,001 – 50,000	40	19.4
	50,001 – 75,000	32	15.5
	75,001 – 1,00,000	14	6.8
	Above 1,00,000	8	3.9
	Total	206	100

The demographic analysis shows an almost equal representation of males (49.5%) and females (50.5%), ensuring balanced participation. Most respondents are below 25 years (65%), followed by the 25–35 years group (22.3%), indicating greater involvement of younger individuals. Students (44.2%) and salaried employees (35%) form the majority,

reflecting higher interest among those with regular income or financial exposure. Over half of the respondents (54.4%) earn below ₹25,000 per month, suggesting that mutual funds are increasingly preferred even among lower- and middle-income groups due to their affordability and flexibility.

2. Gender

206 responses

3. Age Group

206 responses

5. Occupation

206 responses

6. Monthly Income (₹)

206 responses

Awareness of investors towards mutual funds as an investment option:

Variables	Category	No. Respondents	Percentage (%)
Awareness of Mutual Funds	Yes	159	77.2
	No	23	11.2
	Maybe	24	11.6
	Total	206	100
Source of Information	Financial Advisor	50	24.3
	Banks / AMC	40	19.4
	Internet / Social Media	69	33.5
	Friends / Relatives	38	18.4
	Newspapers / Magazines	9	4.4
	Total	206	100

The analysis of awareness and information sources reveals that a significant majority of respondents (77.2%) are aware of mutual funds as an investment option, indicating a high level of awareness among the sample population, while only 11.2% are not aware and 11.6% remain uncertain. With regard to sources of information, the internet and social media emerge as the primary source for 33.5% of

respondents, followed by financial advisors (24.3%) and banks or AMCs (19.4%). Friends and relatives account for 18.4% of information dissemination, whereas newspapers and magazines contribute minimally at 4.4%. This distribution highlights the growing influence of digital platforms in spreading mutual fund awareness, alongside the continued relevance of professional and institutional sources.

7. Are you aware of Mutual Funds as an investment option?

206 responses

8. How long have you been investing in Mutual Funds?

206 responses

Investment pattern and preference of investors towards selected mutual fund schemes:

Variables	Category	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Type of Mutual Fund Preferred	Equity Funds	127	61.7
	Debt Funds	22	10.7
	Hybrid Funds	41	19.9
	Index Funds	11	5.3
	ELSS	5	2.4
	Total	206	100
Investment Mode Preferred	Lump Sum	68	33.0
	SIP (Systematic Investment Plan)	138	67.0
	Total	206	100

The analysis of investment pattern and scheme preference indicates that a majority of respondents (61.7%) prefer equity mutual funds, reflecting a higher inclination towards growth-oriented investment options, followed by hybrid funds (19.9%) which combine both equity and debt features. Debt funds account for 10.7% of preferences, while index funds (5.3%) and ELSS (2.4%) are preferred by a smaller

12. Which type of Mutual Fund do you prefer?

206 responses

proportion of respondents. Regarding the mode of investment, SIP emerges as the most favored option, chosen by 67% of respondents, compared to 33% who prefer lump-sum investments. This trend highlights investors' preference for disciplined, regular investing with reduced risk exposure, indicating growing awareness of long-term wealth creation through systematic investment planning.

13. Which investment mode do you prefer?

206 responses

The risk–return perception of investors regarding mutual fund investments:

Variables	Category	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Risk Tolerance Level	Very Low (1)	56	27.2
	Low (2)	44	21.4
	Moderate (3)	63	30.6
	High (4)	19	9.2
	Very High (5)	23	11.2
Expected Annual Return	Below 8%	38	18.4
	8% – 12%	89	43.2
	12% – 15%	53	25.7
	Above 15%	26	12.6

The analysis of risk and return preferences indicates that most respondents exhibit a moderate risk tolerance, with 30.6% falling in the moderate category, followed by 27.2% having very low risk tolerance and 21.4% low risk tolerance, suggesting an overall cautious investment approach. Only a smaller proportion of respondents display high (9.2%) or very high (11.2%) risk tolerance. In terms of

18. What is your risk tolerance level?

206 responses

expected annual returns, the majority of respondents (43.2%) expect returns in the range of 8%–12%, while 25.7% expect 12%–15% returns and 18.4% are satisfied with returns below 8%. A relatively smaller group (12.6%) expects returns above 15%, indicating that most investors prefer stable and realistic returns aligned with moderate risk-taking behavior.

20. What level of return do you expect from Mutual Funds annually?

206 responses

Satisfaction and Perception:

Variables	Category	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Satisfaction with Mutual Fund Performance	Very Dissatisfied (1)	38	18.4
	Dissatisfied (2)	28	13.6
	Neutral (3)	77	37.4
	Satisfied (4)	33	16.0
	Very Satisfied (5)	30	14.6
Mutual Funds help in achieving Financial Goals	Yes	120	58.3
	No	35	17.0
	To Some Extent	51	24.8
Preference for Mutual Funds over Traditional Investments	Yes	151	73.3
	No	55	26.7
Recommendation of Mutual Funds to Others	Strongly Disagree (1)	34	16.5
	Disagree (2)	20	9.7
	Neutral (3)	70	34.0
	Agree (4)	36	17.5
	Strongly Agree (5)	45	21.8

The analysis of satisfaction and perception reveals that most respondents exhibit a neutral to positive level of satisfaction with the performance of their mutual fund investments, with the largest proportion (37.4%) expressing neutral satisfaction, followed by those who are satisfied (16%) and very satisfied (14.6%), while comparatively fewer respondents report dissatisfaction. A majority of respondents (58.3%) believe that mutual funds help in achieving financial goals, either fully or to some extent,

25. Do you feel Mutual Funds help in achieving financial goals?

206 responses

indicating a favorable perception of mutual funds as an effective investment tool. Furthermore, a significant 73.3% of respondents prefer mutual funds over traditional investment options, reflecting growing investor confidence. In terms of recommendation behavior, 39.3% of respondents agree or strongly agree to recommend mutual fund investments to others, while 34% remain neutral, suggesting overall positive satisfaction with scope for further improvement in investor experience and awareness.

28. Would you recommend Mutual Fund investment to others?

206 responses

26. Do you prefer Mutual Funds over traditional investment options?

206 responses

23. Are you satisfied with the performance of your Mutual Fund investments?

206 responses

Conclusions:

The study highlights the increasing acceptance of mutual funds as a preferred investment option. Awareness levels are high, especially among young and salaried investors, who show a strong preference for equity schemes and systematic investment plans. Most investors display moderate risk tolerance with reasonable return expectations. Factors such as past performance, risk level, fund manager reputation, expense ratio, and brand image significantly influence fund selection. Overall perception towards mutual funds is positive, with most respondents viewing them as effective tools for achieving long-term financial goals and preferring them over traditional investments.

Recommendations:

From the above research, it is recommended that Asset Management Companies (AMCs), financial advisors, and regulatory bodies should take proactive steps to further strengthen investor confidence in mutual funds. Awareness programs and investor education initiatives should be conducted regularly to improve understanding of risk-return characteristics and long-term benefits of mutual fund investments. Special emphasis should be given to promoting

SIPs, as they align well with investors' preference for disciplined and systematic investing.

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